

Initiatives to Stimulate Nuclear Energy Education in the Netherlands

From High-School to Post-Academic Level

Jan Leen Kloosterman^{1*}, Bertie van der Heijdt¹, Robert Beekveldt²

¹Delft University of Technology, Mekelweg 15, Delft, The Netherlands

²NRG PALLAS, Westerduinweg 3, Petten, The Netherlands

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the activities within the Human Capital Agenda setup by the ministry of Climate and Green Growth in the Netherlands to support the governmental plans to expand nuclear energy in the Netherlands with 2-4 large PWR's and multiple SMR's. The initiatives cover a broad field, increasing the interest for nuclear energy at high-schools, expansion of nuclear education at secondary (MBO) and higher (HBO) vocational education institutions, expansion of nuclear education at Delft University of Technology, the only university in the Netherlands with research and education on nuclear fission energy, and delivering post-academic education. In addition, information sessions have been organized for municipalities and governmental bodies and other citizenship's organizations.

Keywords: Human Capital Agenda, Nuclear Energy Education

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Historical developments

The Netherlands has a long history in nuclear research and education. Directly after World War II, in April 1946, the Foundation for Fundamental Research on Matter (FOM) was established to conduct research into atomic and nuclear physics. Almost parallel to this, in 1948, the organization of electricity producers (KEMA) also decided to start nuclear energy research with the aim of eventually building commercial reactors in the Netherlands. This research was led by Dr. Jan Went, who later would become the first professor of nuclear reactor physics in the Netherlands.

Just before WWII, the Dutch government had purchased 10 tons of yellow cake packed in 200 barrels to start research and applications on nuclear fission energy. These barrels were initially stored in Leiden, but just before the outbreak of WW II they were transferred to the basement of the main building of TU Delft [1]. This purchase took place under the guise of the United Glassworks, so that it appeared to be used for coloring glass. Unfortunately, the Netherlands did not have the technology to convert this yellow cake into uranium metal, nor did the Netherlands have the technology to enrich the uranium, which is a prerequisite for achieving a chain reaction with light water as a moderator. This automatically led to a successful collaboration on heavy-water moderated reactors with Norway.

Following the announcement of the Atoms for Peace program, there were increasing calls to build a research reactor using highly enriched uranium as fuel and light water as a moderator and coolant. In January 1954, FOM submitted a proposal for the construction of a 10 MW light-water cooled research reactor, which simultaneously led to declining interest in the Netherlands for the reactor that was being designed in Norway named Natural-Uranium Power-Only-Pile (NUPOP).

Simultaneously, Dr. Jan Went was interested in a variation of an idea developed by Weinberg, who was working in the US on homogeneous liquid reactors. Went wanted to circulate a suspension of small fuel particles in water through metal pipes inserted into a heavy water bath. This concept was called

* J.L.Kloosterman@tudelft.nl

SUSPOP. Through discussions with Walter Zinn, who had worked with Fermi on graphite for the CP1, this idea evolved into the KEMA Suspension Test Reactor (KSTR), which had a strong resemblance to Weinberg's homogeneous reactors.

Meanwhile, on July 6, 1955, the Reactor Center Netherlands was established for the construction of the High Flux Reactor (HFR), which was to be a copy of the Oak Ridge Research Reactor, but with a special irradiation facility in which a circuit could be placed. This was Went's idea, so that he could test the suspension test reactor in a radiation field. The HFR reached full power in 1963.

Of course people also had to be trained in the nuclear field. In 1955, summer schools were organized in Delft, and in September 1956, Dr. Went became the first professor in nuclear reactor technology, which marked the start of nuclear education at TU Delft. Prof. Jan Went was followed up by Dr. Klein (1963), who had a strong interest in metal-cooled fast reactors, Prof. Hugo van Dam (1971), Prof. Tim van der Hagen (1997), and Prof. Jan Leen Kloosterman (2010).

In preparation for the construction of a reactor for research and education at TU Delft, the Dutch government purchased in 1956 a small nuclear reactor in the US with a supply agreement for the fissile material. This (critical!) reactor was shown to the public during a major exhibition at Schiphol Airport [1]. The reactor had a power of 10 kW and used fuel plates with enrichment of 20%.

After the exhibition, some components and the fuel were transferred to Delft, where they awaited use in the Higher Education Reactor (HOR). Because the quality of the 20% enriched fuel was insufficient, it was ultimately decided to use highly enriched fuel. The reactor in Delft would therefore start in 1963 using 93% enriched fuel, but converted to 20% enrichment in 2005.

In the same decade, other research reactors were built in the Netherlands, like the Low Flux Reactor in Petten (LFR, 10 kW Argonaut, 1960-2010), the Biological Agricultural Reactor Netherlands in Wageningen (BARN, 100 kW, 1963-1980), and the Atomic reactor TH Eindhoven Netherlands (ATHENE, 10 kW Argonaut, 1969-1973).

Also two nuclear power plants were constructed, being the 50 MWe BWR in Dodewaard (1969-1997) employing natural circulation of cooling water in the primary vessel, and the 500 MWe PWR in Borssele (1973). The latter is still in operation and studies are being performed to judge whether lifetime extension beyond 2033 is feasible. Furthermore, the Netherlands participated in the SNR-300 sodium-cooled fast reactor in Kalkar (Germany).

1.2. Current developments

While the sentiments with regard to the civil use of nuclear energy have long been mostly negative throughout most of the Western-European countries, i.a. through the accidents at the Chernobyl- and Fukushima reactors, the attitude towards nuclear energy has over the last 4-5 years been rapidly changing due to the growing need for reliable carbon free energy sources in the light of the EU-targets for reduction of CO₂ emissions to the atmosphere. This is clearly also the case in the Netherlands. As a result, the Dutch government has formulated new policies towards prominent incorporation of nuclear energy in the energy mix. These new policies aim at allowing the (single) operating NPP at Borssele to extend its lifespan beyond 2033, which could extend the total life time of this power plant to 70 or 80 years. Currently it is being investigated whether this is technically and economically feasible. Furthermore, the government aims to establish 2-4 new Gen-III+ NPPs in the Netherlands, preferably in the province of Zeeland close to the existing power plant, and is also defining new policies to facilitate third parties (private investors, industrial conglomerates, provinces, municipalities) wishing to establish small modular reactors (SMR) in the Netherlands.

In addition to these power plant initiatives, the 25 MWth PALLAS reactor, meant primarily for isotope production but also for nuclear research, is under construction in Petten as the successor of the HFR.

2. HUMAN CAPITAL AGENDA

As the Dutch nuclear sector, though diverse, is currently quite small, the new Dutch nuclear ambitions require major investments in attracting and training of a new nuclear workforce. In order to get a clearer picture of how the future workforce should look like, both in size and needed expertise /

qualification and educational levels, various studies have been performed during the last years. The most recent and most in depth study to date has been done by Technopolis in 2024 [2]. In this study, estimates with respect to the size and qualifications of the required new workforce have been made, based on three different scenarios, with timeline shown in Figure 1:

1. Life time extension of the Borssele NPP beyond 2033, plus 2 new Gen-III+ NPPs.
2. As scenario 1, with the addition of 2 extra Gen III+ NPPs
3. As scenario 2, with the addition of 5 SMRs

Figure 1: The three scenarios in the Netherlands and their respective time lines [2].

At present, almost 2000 FTE are employed in the Dutch nuclear sector, which is already a growth of roughly 20 percent compared to 2021. So clearly various relevant organizations have already been anticipating to what is expected to come in the light of the new nuclear renaissance. But in practice, the future need for new human capital will be excessively higher than the extrapolation of the current growth rate could ever accommodate. Technopolis [2] reports a required workforce of roughly 4,000 FTE in a scenario where four new NPPs (GEN III+) are constructed, which represents a doubling of the sector's workforce compared to present numbers. This demand is projected for the period around 2040, once all new builds have been realized. This projection, which will increase further if also Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) become operational, demands an influx of personnel that seems unrealistic to accomplish solely through the nuclear educational programs currently offered by Dutch institutions. So clearly, investments in the establishment of additional nuclear training options at all levels (vocational, BSc, MSc) are a strong prerequisite to make (any of) the described scenarios feasible.

Clearly though, the biggest challenge with respect to human capital will not be the operational stage, but the period in time when the new planned nuclear infrastructure is being built. During that period, that will roughly last until 2040, would at its height require a workforce of 8000-14500, depending on the scenario considered [2].

Although part of this workforce will be at the BSc, MSc and PhD level, a larger percentage (up to 60-70%) will be at the vocational level and will not be specifically and extensively 'nuclear educated'. Nevertheless also for these workers, sufficient training and qualifications to be able to work in a nuclear setting and perform their tasks according to the various nuclear codes and standards related to new builds will be mandatory. The Technopolis report [2] states that it is expected that only one third of this workforce will actually be from the Netherlands, with the other two thirds needing to come from abroad, either brought in by the vendors or (temporarily) hired for specific projects.

So with respect to human capital, two major challenges need to be addressed to be able to realize the Dutch policies and plans with respect to new build NPPs:

- The fact that the current nuclear educational infrastructure in the Netherlands, with just one Dutch university actually offering a nuclear science and technology program, and hardly any nuclear curricula being offered at the vocational- or polytechnical high school level, is grossly insufficient to fulfill the Dutch growing demands for new nuclear human capital.

- The fact that at present also many other countries, both in Europe (i.a. France, Czech Republic, Poland, United Kingdom) and worldwide, are planning, developing or even already actively building new NPPs, thereby partly competing for the same (international) workforce,

Therefore, the ministry responsible for energy policy, including the incorporation of nuclear energy, is since 2023 actively investing in the nuclear human capital agenda, i.e. through subsidies for educational institutions to develop nuclear curricula and through financing of the Nuclear Academy, a joint initiative of NRG-PALLAS and the TU Delft, established to support educational institutions in the development of nuclear educational programs and through all sorts of activities with the objective to attract new technical students from various backgrounds to the nuclear domain.

3. NUCLEAR ACADEMY

3.1. Goal of the Nuclear Academy

To develop a sufficiently qualified workforce capable of realizing the Netherlands' ambitions in nuclear energy, an ecosystem must be created in which all stakeholders — educational institutions, government bodies, nuclear companies and operators, technology suppliers, and the wider supply chain — collaborate and develop education and training programs in nuclear technology.

For this reason, NRG PALLAS and Delft University of Technology (TU Delft), with funding from the Dutch government, launched the Nuclear Academy in 2023, with the goal to establish a self-sustaining ecosystem of nuclear technology education and training. This ecosystem will help ensure a sufficient supply of qualified personnel to achieve the Netherlands' nuclear ambitions.

3.2. Activities in the Nuclear Academy

The Nuclear Academy focuses on the following activities:

- Developing curricula at secondary and higher vocational levels to educate students and career changers in nuclear technology. This includes training the teachers and supporting educational institutions in developing applied research programs where relevant.
- Establishing a national nuclear knowledge platform, connecting educational institutions and other stakeholders for knowledge sharing and coordination.
- Providing information sessions and technical training for government agencies and regulators, aimed at increasing nuclear literacy within the public sector.
- Inspiring and informing high school students, career changers, and students in vocational, bachelor, and university programs to increase the inflow of talent into nuclear education and the wider sector.
- Supporting outreach activities that help Dutch industry qualify for participation in the nuclear new-build supply chain.
- Exchanging best practices through international collaboration on the development of a qualified nuclear workforce.

The Nuclear Academy is managed by three dedicated professionals, supported by a pool of nuclear experts from NRG PALLAS and TU Delft. This structure ensures a lean operation while integrating high-level nuclear expertise into our programs.

3.3. Results to date in the Nuclear Academy

Since its founding, the Nuclear Academy has focused on informing educational institutions about the opportunities and future perspectives of nuclear technology in light of national ambitions and government plans. Because most educational institutions had limited prior knowledge of nuclear topics, awareness sessions have played a key role in building interest, which has since grown significantly. Since 2024, the following results have been achieved:

MoU between vocational education, the nuclear sector, and the Nuclear Academy

In January 2024, a memorandum of understanding was signed, initiated by the Nuclear Academy, between four vocational education institutions and several key players in the nuclear sector. This agreement represents a major milestone in embedding nuclear technology within Dutch vocational education. Signatories included NRG PALLAS, TU Delft, COVRA, EPZ, and Urenco, along with the vocational institutions Scalda, Vonk, Talland College, and ROC Twente.

Secondary vocational-level elective module developed and implemented

In September 2024, the first nuclear elective module was successfully introduced at Scalda, a secondary vocational education institution, as a co-creation between the Nuclear Academy and Scalda, with 20 students participating. The module has a total study load of 240 hours and is based on standard Radiation Protection (RPE) courses, delivered one day per week over a period of 18 weeks. It covers topics such as radioactivity, the interaction of ionizing radiation with matter, biological effects, and radiation measurement. Additionally, the module includes basic nuclear safety training in a mock-up facility of NPP Borssele. During this exercise, students practice the standard operational cycle of work preparation, execution—including a 'nuclear transition' (controlled zone entry)—and evaluation. To showcase various nuclear environments, the program also features visits to COVRA (Dutch Radioactive Waste Facility), the NPP Borssele, and a regional Hospital.

Higher vocational-level minor developed and implemented

In February 2025, HZ University of Applied Sciences, a higher vocational education institution nearby the NPP Borssele, launched the first Nuclear Technology minor (30 ECTS), developed in collaboration with the Nuclear Academy, enrolling 21 students in the first year. The program will be offered annually. The minor includes the topics like: radiation protection, reactor physics, reactor technology, safety culture, fuel cycle, operation and maintenance.

Teach-the-teacher program launched

To enable educational institutions to deliver nuclear curricula independently, the Nuclear Academy launched a one-week "teach-the-teacher" program in 2025. Teachers receive training in radiation protection, reactor physics, reactor technology, safety culture, and the nuclear fuel cycle.

Innovative learning tools

A Virtual Reality (VR) platform has been developed with three nuclear training scenarios, including a simulation of a radiological laboratory. Vocational and bachelor-level institutions are granted free access to this platform. Recently, a software simulator of a Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) has been acquired. This simulator will be implemented in the curricula to provide students with hands-on experience in reactor operation and system behavior.

Workshops and technical courses for government agencies

The Nuclear Academy has developed several introductory and technical courses to enhance nuclear knowledge within local and national government institutions.

Student engagement activities

The Nuclear Academy organized a nuclear introduction week for vocational students, during which they explored nuclear applications in healthcare, offshore industries, and the energy sector.

Additionally, a summer school was held in collaboration with SCK-CEN (Belgian Nuclear Research Centre), where students visited nuclear facilities in the Netherlands and Belgium and attended various lectures (see Figure 2). With an average evaluation score of 9.5/10 the program was greatly appreciated.

The Nuclear Academy will continue to be funded by the Dutch government until at least 2030. Together with educational institutions, government bodies, and industry partners, it will further strengthen the national ecosystem for nuclear education and training, contributing to a skilled workforce the Netherlands needed to meet its nuclear energy goals.

Figure 2: The participants of the first Belgian-Dutch summer school.

4. ACADEMIC NUCLEAR EDUCATION

4.1. Nuclear Education at TU Delft

In the Netherlands, there is two academic programs on nuclear energy. One focusing on nuclear fission energy at TU Delft and one on nuclear fusion energy at TU Eindhoven. The latter runs a specialized nuclear fusion master program attracting several tens of students each year. The education at TU Delft, being much larger, is organized differently and focuses on large generic master programs with specializations, e.g. a nuclear specialization within chemical engineering, mechanical engineering, or applied physics. In practice, students get a similar amount or even more of nuclear education as in nuclear master programs at some other universities (especially those with only one-year master programs), but this is rather invisible to the outside. This is clearly a disadvantage for the student who want to continue his/her career in the nuclear field, because the amount of nuclear education followed by the student is not directly visible to future employers.

It has however some advantages as well.

1. The master program at TU Delft takes two years (120 ec), of which about 2/3 can be filled with nuclear related courses, a nuclear graduation project and a nuclear internship. This leaves ample opportunities for the student to broaden in other fields as well.
2. Students will graduate with a diploma of the master program with a generic title (e.g. engineer in Applied Physics), keeping options open for a career outside the nuclear field. As a consequence, a choice for a nuclear energy specialization does not block other career opportunities and is felt by the student as a non-regret option. This helps the student to keep options open, and has helped our nuclear education program to survive during stagnation in nuclear energy. TU Delft has always had sufficient students entering nuclear specializations, and the students always found jobs, in- or outside the nuclear field.
3. The nuclear education followed by a student will primarily be in the field of his/her interest. For example a Chemical Engineering student can follow more chemically oriented nuclear courses, while Applied Physics students more physics oriented nuclear courses. This has always led to highly-motivated high-quality graduates with in-depth specialization.

Besides education on nuclear energy, TU Delft has expanded during last decades on nuclear research and education in the nuclear medical field, covering the topics of radionuclide production, nuclear imaging, internal radiation therapy (using radionuclides), external radiation therapy (using protons), and many more. As much as possible use is made of the nuclear research reactor at TU Delft, or of the Holland Particle Therapy Center (HPTC) built at the premises of the TU Delft Reactor Institute.

4.2. Expansion and developments

As mentioned before, the Dutch government wishes to expand on nuclear energy, first with a few large PWRs as a base for the expected increase of our electricity consumption, and at a later stage with SMRs to deliver a more distributed power generation, with the possibility of cogeneration. For the two (or perhaps even four) large PWRs, the government has reserved a large multi-billion euro budget to support site selection, reactor selection, licensing, construction and operation.

To initiate nuclear education and to develop the Human Capital Agenda (HCA) in the nuclear field as well as to support nuclear innovation programs in the Netherlands, the Dutch government has reserved 65 million euro, while an equal amount has been reserved to support the site selection and licensing of multiple SMRs in the Netherlands.

TU Delft has always had in place and kept alive a nuclear education and research program both on fission energy and the health domain. A few years ago, part of the HCA budget of the government has been allocated to install at TU Delft four new chairs on Radiation Dosimetry, Nuclear Reactor Physics, Nuclear Energy Technology and Nuclear Materials Science.

With this comes a moral obligation to revitalize nuclear education in the Netherlands. Obviously the four new chairs will lead to new nuclear courses, and more research topics for bachelor and master students to perform their graduation project (15 ec for bachelor, 45 ec for master projects). Furthermore TU Delft is revitalizing exercises with reactor software simulators, with our DELPHI subcritical assembly, and with our TU Delft research reactor (see Figure 3). Currently we have in place a software simulator of our own reactor, but recently contracted the use of a PWR simulator developed by BUTE (Budapest). DELPHI is a subcritical assembly established about 20 years ago [3] which we are revitalizing with new detectors and a new Californium source. DELPHI contains 168 fuel pins (3.8% enriched) that can be loaded in a water tank. It can be used for the measurement of approach to critical, axial and radial flux profiles, source jerk experiments, and neutron noise measurements (Feynman alpha and correlation measurements) [4,5]. In addition, our TU Delft research reactor has had an upgrade including the implementation of a cold neutron source boosting our neutron scattering, reflectometry and imaging instruments with a factor of 50-100. We are reintroducing a practical for students in which they can startup our reactor under supervision of a senior operator.

Although the organization model with educational specializations in large master programs worked well to educate nuclear engineers in the Netherlands, the new nuclear renaissance we are facing attracts many students willing to follow a full and visible nuclear master program. Currently we are studying the possibilities of a full nuclear master program at TU Delft, possibly with input from other universities in the Netherlands as well.

Figure 3: The TU Delft Reactor Institute (left) and the subcritical assembly DELPHI (right).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The governmental initiative to expand nuclear energy in the Netherlands has led to a Human Capital Agenda aiming at increasing the interest for nuclear energy at high-schools, expansion of nuclear education at secondary (MBO) and higher (HBO) vocational education institutions, expansion of nuclear education at TU Delft, the only university in the Netherlands with research and education on nuclear fission energy, and post-academic education. In addition information sessions have been organized for municipalities and governmental bodies and other citizenship's organizations.

NOMENCLATURE

FOM Foundation for Fundamental Research on Matter, HCA Human Capital Agenda, HFR High Flux Reactor, HOR Hoger Onderwijs Reactor (TU Delft research reactor), HPTC Holland Particle Therapy Center, HZ Hogeschool Zeeland.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Hugo van Dam en Frida de Jong, "Geboeid door Straling en Strategie". ISBN 90 5730 232 2 (2003).
- [2] Technopolis, "Human Capital voor Kernenergie". [Technopolis report \(2024\)](#) (2024).
- [3] J.L. Kloosterman, "DELPHI: a New Subcritical Assembly at Delft University of Technology", Conference Paper Title". In Proceedings of the PHYSOR 2004. American Nuclear Society, Chicago, Illinois, USA (2004).
- [4] Máté Szieberth, Gergely Klujber, Jan Leen Kloosterman, Dick de Haas, "Neutron Noise Measurements at the DELPHI Subcritical Assembly". In Proceedings of the PHYSOR 2012, Knoxville, Tenn., USA (2012).
- [5] Máté Szieberth, Gergely Klujber, Jan Leen Kloosterman, Dick de Haas, "Measurement of multiple alpha-modes at the Delphi subcritical assembly by neutron noise techniques", *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, 75:146-157 (2015).